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XALQARO ILMIIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI

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FORMATION AND ELIMINATION OF GROWTHS THROUGH THE GAS TRACT OF THE VANYUKOV FURNACE COMPLEX

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Abstract. The study examines the causes of growth formation on the walls of the Vanyukov furnace steam-boiler and ways to eliminate them.

Keywords: Vanyukov furnace, off-gas stream, growth, natural gas, petroleum coke.

Introduction

Panels of the steam-boiler of the Vanyukov furnace, and filters remains one of the pressing operational problems. These formations negatively affect the thermal regime, gas dynamics, and the equipment's service life.

Methods

Natural gas supplied through tuyeres actively participates in heat generation:

- Complete combustion ($\text{CH}_4 + 2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (water vapor) + Q) - ensures stable temperature in the reaction zone.

- Incomplete combustion ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2 + \text{Q}$) - creates a reducing atmosphere, affects desulfurization, and can contribute to the reduction of CuO to Cu [1].

Using petroleum coke instead of natural gas has given less opportunities in terms of heat generation, but has greater efficiency for the gas line ($\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$). Chemical reactions at the solid-liquid phase interface proceed more intensively than in the liquid gas phase. Values of Gibbs energy and equilibrium constant of chemical reactions occurring during coke combustion at different temperatures are indicated in (table 1).

To prevent growth formation, the following measures are applied:

1. Optimization of slag composition
 - Control of the Fe/SiO₂ ratio;
 - Maintaining low slag viscosity;
 - Regulation of lime (CaO 1-3%), quartz, and coke additives.
2. Stabilization of the heat regime
 - Leveling the temperature fields in the furnace and gas pipeline;
 - Reduction of sharp temperature fluctuations.
3. Improvement of gas distribution
 - Controlling the speed and direction of the gas flow;
 - Rearrangement of burners for uniform heat distribution;
 - Reduction of vortex and local overheating zones [2].
4. Cleaning of panels and heat exchange surfaces
 - Application of gas-pulse purification (impact waves of a mixture of compressed gas, air, and oxygen);
 - Regular mechanical cleaning and surface diagnostics of heat exchangers;
 - Increasing efficiency by reducing the thermal resistance of panels

Table 1

№	Substance		Chemical reaction	
	Petroleum coke burning		$\text{C} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CO}_2$	
	T, K	T, °C	$\Delta G^T, \text{kJ}$	K
1	298	25	-394.37	1.1726
2	398	125	-394.66	1.1267
3	498	225	-394.95	1.1001
4	598	325	-395.24	1.0827
5	698	425	-395.53	1.0705

6	798	525	-395.82	1.0615
7	898	625	-396.11	1.0545
8	998	725	-396.39	1.0489
9	1098	825	-396.68	1.0444
10	1198	925	-396.97	1.0406
11	1298	1025	-397.26	1.0375
12	1398	1125	-397.55	1.0348
13	1498	1225	-397.84	1.0324
14	1598	1325	-398.13	1.0304

Results

The advantage of using petroleum coke instead of natural gas with thermodynamic patterns has been confirmed in practice. Growth on the walls of the furnace, panels of the steam-boiler has significantly been diminished.

Discussion

The Vanyukov furnace remains a highly efficient unit for processing copper-containing concentrates, however, its operational stability is directly dependent on the control of growth formation. The latter are formed under the influence of chemical-physical, thermal, and operational factors. The use of natural gas, despite its effectiveness in temperature stabilization, can contribute to the formation of growths when the supply and composition of the charge are incorrectly adjusted.

Conclusion

The problem can be solved through a comprehensive approach: optimizing the charge, managing gas and heat regimes, and regularly cleaning the equipment. This will ensure reliable operation, reduce metal losses, and improve the environmental performance of production.

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DUNYO AMALIYOTIDA GRAFITNI BOYITISH TEXNOLOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada dunyo amaliyotida grafitni boyitishning asosiy texnologiyalari, ularning afzallik va kamchiliklari, yirik konlar va mamlakatlar tajribasi, shuningdek ekologik muammolar va istiqbollar tahlil qilinadi. Grafitning sanoatdagi o'rni, uni boyitish texnologik sxemalari, yangi reagentlar va innovatsion yondashuvlar haqida keng qamrovli ma'lumot beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: grafit, boyitish, flotatsiya, magnit ajratish, kimyoviy tozalash, ekologiya.

Kirish. Grafit – noyob mineral bo'lib, elektr va issiqlik o'tkazuvchanligi, kimyoviy inertligi va yuqori mustahkamligi tufayli turli sanoat tarmoqlarida asosiy xomashyo sifatida ishlatiladi. Hozirgi vaqtda global bozorda grafitga bo'lgan talab, ayniqsa elektr transport vositalari (EV) va superkondensatorlar ishlab chiqarish sohalarida sezilarli darajada ortmoqda. Shuning uchun grafitni boyitish texnologiyalarini chuqur o'rganish ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.